

DETERMINATION OF THE OPTIMAL VALUES OF THE PARAMETERS OF THE COMBINED MACHINE

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In our country, crops such as autumn wheat, which is planted on fields vacated by repeated crops, and vegetables and potatoes, which are planted as repeated crops on fields vacated by it, are planted on new, i.e., plowed areas before direct planting. In this case, plowed land is prepared for continuous planting, and then planting events are held.

In our republic, the preparation of plowed land for planting has been carried out many times separately with gear and disc studs and various mola-rectifiers. This leads to deterioration of the physical and mechanical properties of the soil, the loss of a lot of moisture from the soil and an increase in fuel consumption and other costs. An analysis of scientific achievements on a global scale and previously carried out research in our Republic shows that these shortcomings in the preparation of new plowed lands for planting can be eliminated by developing a machine that will perform all technological processes for preparing the soil for planting in one transition from the field (complete compaction of the plowing layer, leveling and grinding the surface). Applying such a machine before planting on freshly plowed land allows you to carry out technological processes by adding and sharply reduce fuel consumption and other costs at the expense of reducing the number of aggregates from field to field, increase work productivity, improve the quality of soil processing and prevent the loss of moisture in it, plant crops on time.

From the above, a machine was developed that processed the plowed land in the Khmiti, and an experimental copy of it was prepared and tested [1;2].

This article describes the results of multi-factor experiments conducted to determine the optimal values of the parameters of the developed combined machine

gear-planked reel.

Table 1 lists factors, their designation, range of variation, and levels.

When conducting multi-factor experiments, the level of soil abrasion in 0-10 layers, that is, the amount of fractions less than 25 mm in size (Y1,%), density (Y2, g/sm³) and the specific resistance of the cartilaginous to drag (Y3, N/M), was adopted as an assessment criterion. In doing so, it was seen that the second-order polynomial fully illuminates the influence of factors on the evaluation criteria, and the experiments were carried out on the V4 plan. [2].

In order to reduce the impact of uncontrollable factors on evaluation criteria, the sequence of conducting experiments was established using a table of random numbers [3]. In addition in experiments, for all options, the angle of installation of the reel planks relative to its axis was taken to be 15°.

Table 1.

Factor designation, levels, and change intervals

Naming of factors	Unit of measurement	Marking of factors	Factors-of variation al range	Levels of factors		
				(-1)	(0)	(+1)
1. Планкали ғалтакмоланинг диаметри, D	см	X_1	5	35	40	45
2. Ғалтакмолага ўрнатилаган планкалар сони, n	дона	X_2	2	8	10	12
3. Планкали ғалтакмолага бериладиган тик юкланиш, Q	Н/м	X_3	100	700	800	900

- 0-10 см қатламдаги тупроқнинг уваланиш даражаси бўйича (%)

The data obtained in the experiments were processed according to the "PLANEXP" program developed in the experimental planning Laboratory of Qxmiti. In this, the Cochran criterion was used in assessing the uniformity of dispersion, the

Student criterion in assessing the value of regression coefficients, and the Fisher criterion in assessing the adequacy of regression models.

The following regression equations were obtained, which were processed in the order indicated for the results of the experiment and adequately expressed the evaluation criteria:

- By the level of soil abrasion in a layer of 0-10 CM (%)

$$Y_1 = +80,136 - 0,980X_1 + 1,674X_2 + 1,830X_3 + 2,494X_4 + \\ +0,614X_1X_1 - 0,588X_1X_2 - 0,583X_1X_3 - 0,583X_1X_4 - 0,936X_2X_2 - \\ -0,587X_2X_3 - 0,588X_2X_4 + 0,498X_3X_3 - 0,592X_3X_4 - 0,652X_4X_4 \quad (1)$$

- By the density of the soil in a layer of 0-10 CM (g / cm³)

$$Y_2 = +1,121 - 0,030X_1 + 0,026X_2 + 0,033X_3 - 0,060X_4 + \\ +0,017X_1X_1 + 0,024X_1X_2 + 0,055X_1X_3 - 0,014X_1X_4 - 0,038X_2X_2 + \\ +0,006X_2X_3 + 0,010X_2X_4 + 0,013X_3X_3 + 0,013X_3X_4 + 0,040X_4X_4 \quad (2)$$

$$Y_3 = +214,534 - 16,926X_1 + 14,870X_2 + 14,593X_3 + \\ +27,315X_4 + 13,299X_1X_1 + 1,937X_1X_4 + 8,799X_2X_2 - \\ -3,368X_3X_3 + 1,937X_3X_4 + 7,799X_4X_4 \quad (3)$$

The obtained regression equations were derived from one in such a way that all the factors largely met the criteria of bexpolash. The regression of the U1-meson equations is more than 80%, the U2-meson is 1.1-1.2 g/cm³ in the medium, the U3-meson has a minimum kiimat solved from bylish conditions, and the possession of the parameters in the galtakmolat song in the operating speed range of 6.0-8.0 km/h was analyzed.

For example, galtacmoles at operating speeds of 6.0-8.0 km/h consume less energy on the surface of the fields, in order to provide the computer with high-quality work at the required level, they have diameters of 39.38-40.06 cm, retractable Sony slats of 10 pcs and a steep load. this value should be exceeded with an interval of 0.83-0.86 kn. In this case, the degree of salivation is 80.48-82.03%, the density of salivation

in folds 10-20 cm long is 1.12-1.18 g/cm³, and tie the galtacmole to the stretch
214-transports 239 N/m.

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Gearbox plankali galtakmola 6.0-8.0 km / h with low energy consumption supplied to the surface of the fields at operating speeds to ensure high-quality work in fields in demand for export, their diameter should be 39.38-40.06 cm, adjustable straps Sony 10 pcs. and the steepness of the installation provided for them must correspond to be driven at an interval of 0.83-0.86 kn. In this case, the resistance to salting of the soil is 80.48 - 82.03%, the density of the soil in folds 10-20 cm thick is 1.12–1.18 g / cm³, and the resistance to salting of galtacmole is 214-239 n / m.

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